

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B507		
Date:	31/01/10		
Take Off:	09:53:38Z	Z	Z
Landing:	15:16:09Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 22m 31s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Atlantic/ NW Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voden	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Paul Barrett	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	CVI / Mission Scientist Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
9	Mini-LIDAR	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
11	Mission 2	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
Y	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
Y	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
Y	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (Weather Radar)
	Planning charts or plots
Y	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-31	Flight Manager	Initial version
R1			
r2			

09:39:05-47:39:04

GLon_PARA0611, GLot_PARA0610

B507, 31 Jan 2010 CONSTRRAIN FLIGHT 12

Sortie S5: Ice nucleation and secondary ice multiplication in super-cooled Cumulus.

Super-cooled Cumulus are required for observations of mixed-phase studies, where ice nucleation, secondary ice multiplication and warm-rain processes are important. Secondary ice multiplication from splintering during the riming growth of ice particles is active between -3°C and -8°C .

Both the intensity and duration of surface precipitation depends on warm-rain processes (auto-conversion of cloud liquid) and ice-phase processes.

Weather Northerly Airflow over warm sea track

Sortie location

Northwest – Stornoway

Sortie summary

Sample a growing Cumulus with a series of ascending straight and level runs.

Alternatively, if there are many Cumulus, sample each by a series of long straight and level runs at specified altitudes.

Cloud penetrations should allow at least 60sec wings level before entering and after leaving cloud to allow for aerosol characterisation

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area (NW of Lewis) at best-range speed and altitude. To 58.5N, 6.5W
- 2) **SLR SURVEY at Altitude** In a box defined by 6.5W, 7.0W, 58.5N and northern limit along line of cloud streets
- 3) **Drop A Sonde** at mid way point,
- 4) **Profile descent at northern limit**(stepped to stay in region, avoiding cloud penetrations) to reach minimum altitude below target clouds.
- 5) **Aerosol characterisation run 500ft below cloud base** back along line of clouds
- 6) **Climb into cloud and perform SLR runs along a line of clouds** starting at 500ft above cloud base
- 7) **Wings must be level** for cloud penetrations to ensure good data quality
- 8) **Climb in turn onto reciprocal track at specified height**
- 9) **Deicing Legs** – if icing occurs during a run descend below freezing level. Subsequently ascend to last racetrack level.
- 10) **Stepped Profile Descent through cloud** in a stairwell-fashion profile descent with cloud penetrations at similar altitudes as those on ascent
- 11) **Repeat 6-10**
- 12) **Drop a sonde through region over the sea during return transit**
- 13) **Transit to Prestwick at best range speed and altitude**

Instrument requirements

Lidar

CVI operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode, except for the sub-cloud run which is in aerosol mode.

Cloud physics to report the time when first ice particles are observed during each of the cloud penetration runs.

Crew:

1. Captain - Luc Lathouwers (Directflight)
2. Co-pilot - Alan Foster Directflight)
3. CCM - Robbie Voaden (Directflight)
4. Mission Scientist – Paul Barrett (Met Office)
5. Flight Manager – Alan Wooley (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics - Martyn Pickering (Met Office)
7. AVAPS - Doug Anderson* (FAAM)
8. Mini-LIDAR / FWVS - Dave Pollard (Met Office)
9. CVI - Kirsty McBeath (Met Office)
10. Manchester Cloud - James Dorsey (University of Manchester)
11. Mission Scientist 2 - Keith Bower (University of Manchester)

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B507

Date: 31/1/10

Project:CONSTRAIN

Location:Hebrides

Start End

Time Time Event Height (s) Hdg Comments

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
094440		startup	0.29 kft	024	
094836		taxy	0.29 kft	026	
095338		T/O	0.28 kft	301	
103728	105747	Run 1	20.1 - 20.0 kft	342	
103728		Sonde 1	20.1 kft	340	
105752	111753	Profile 1	20.0 - 0.23 kft	335	
111754	111932	Profile 2	0.24 - 1.8 kft	119	
111932	113309	Run 2	1.8 kft	129	
112020		qnh 1004	1.8 kft	130	
113041		jw/nevz zero	1.8 kft	147	
113514	113712	Run 3	3.8 - 3.9 kft	334	
113917	114038	Run 4	4.8 kft	337	
114112	115843	Run 5	5.2 - 5.3 kft	334	
120149	121906	Run 6	6.3 kft	157	
122203	124208	Run 7	6.8 kft	319	
124548	125117	Run 8	7.3 - 7.2 kft	142	
125521	130009	Run 9	7.8 - 7.7 kft	351	
130230	130602	Run 10	8.3 kft	154	
130926	131428	Run 11	8.3 kft	337	
131608	132102	Run 12	8.3 kft	169	
132443	132830	Run 13	8.9 - 8.8 kft	348	
133148	133703	Run 14	8.8 kft	173	
134035	134450	Run 15	8.8 kft	339	
134837	135255	Run 16	8.8 kft	162	
135620	140036	Run 17	9.0 kft	351	
140418	140825	Run 18	8.3 kft	175	
141222	141609	Run 19	8.3 kft	340	
142150		Sonde 2	12.0 kft	168	
142212	142746	Profile 3	12.0 - 6.8 kft	159	
143158	143352	Profile 3	6.8 - 5.1 kft	331	resume
143821	143949	Profile 3	5.0 - 3.8 kft	158	resume
144037	144505	Profile 3	3.7 - 0.25 kft	160	resume
151609		Land	0.26 kft	303	Prestwick

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B506**..... Date 30-01-10 Name PBARRETT..... Page 1 of 12

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
093500					start up
					Lat I.R. shows cloud regions
					as expected
					Expecting wind at 350
					Early T-0
					Climb out - shows visible horizon
					Expect (w/d) Area, -high tops
					ice in cloud,
					1/3 scattered C ₀ @ 20000ft
					- check - Sat I.R. US,
					LIDAR, cloud tops
					Nav, JW, Arctical occurrence
					355 AK winds @ 355 ft
					Horace = 351
1A. 07. 00					Transit @ AL 200, shows visible

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**⁵⁰⁶... Date 30 01-10 Name P. BARRETT... Page 2 of 12...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1026					Latest visible shows N → cloud
				⊕	development, isolated but numerous showers
				⊕	extensive C _u through broken S _c visually
1029 57					↳ LIDAR - top @ 5000, some breaks.
1031 17	R1	200	343		some development below but flat S _c ahead, clouds have developed to left
					LIDAR 8.04A 50% coverage with breaks down to 1000,
1037					LIDAR Top to 10.5 coverage in sea
1058 33					SONDE GONE WINDS ARE now 348°
					LIDAR top 6.7, no breaks but surface clouds through thinner S _c
1056 36	R1 END 9:20				+ sonde in water
	P1				LIDAR - more contiguous toward end of run
					Profile to the left of A-B to allow descent through clear S _c .

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 31.01.10 Flight No: B 507 Pre-Flighter: STEVE COLLIER

No.	✓ or ✗	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	<u>500 147</u> <u>138</u>
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	<u>N₂ = 56 bar CO₂/Ar = 138 bar</u>
3	✓	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	✓	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & check on <u>AUTO</u>	
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	<u>In cockpit</u>
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	✗	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	✗	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	✗	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	✗	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	✓	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or ✗	Location	Action	Comments
30	✓	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	✗	CCN SS coils A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	✓	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	✗	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	✓	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	✗	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36		Core Chemistry	O ₃ /NO _x /CO zeros performed Ok	
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	✗	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48	✓	All other covers	Removed	
49	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
50	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
52	✓	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	Signed
53	✓	ICEX	applied	
54	✓	Turb Probe - Traps	emptied, detail contents -	
				a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146

update on the tennis.
with that or do others want to watch it on iplayer later?
I here
iplayer later
close though. Lots of rallies
sending updates

2:1 to Fed
is your fine?! Richard has just told me.

ing tired
new top on
sweaty!

2nd set :-(
d then ... on the plus side nice wave cloud on our RHS
ard that!
Murray!

est wind is about 30deg off N from west, Turb probe 340-345, aircraft 330 & 351 deg

e turb probe.
e with height as it was yesterday, so need to stick to your guns.
at start of R1 should help too
a new racket
Murray

a bit
sonde? Useful?

g to turn? It is hard to tell from the track plot.
ate plot - you are heading the right direction.
howing best to the west rather than the east.
smaller than yesterday.
pleased

ost comms for a while at base of P1]

showing best to the west rather than the east.
smaller than yesterday.
pleased

ing to him

hurray
@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146
conditions looking today?

FAAM_MS3
FAAM_MS3
FAAM_MS3
FAAM_MS3
FAAM_MS3

escent now lidar tops on a street 8 to 9 turetsto 11kft bases 3000ft
FAAM_MS3

@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146

yl
ug only part of the sonde message was transmitted?

et

FAAM_MS3
meant set 3 not set 4 on previous chats.
FAAM_MS3

Scotsman lost !! lost comms for a while at base of P1
s will NOT be science.
u ask Dave P if he is happy to travel back in Richard's car, or does he want to go to Cranfield?
3 6-4 7-6 (13-11)

ost comms for a while at base of P1|

6 + nt - <No topic is set >

ask Dave P if he is happy to travel back in Richard's car, or does he want to go to Cranfield?

3 6-4 7-6 (13-11)

B messy now at 5kft in/ouy clod

Richard lift on Tues

uds are go going in & out of?

oks very structured and that you are in the right place.

[@i.love.debian.org](#) has joined #faam146

ou in the profile again?

like to know ow many clouds you are going trough per run and what the ice phase is.

ixed at 6.5kft. Also questions about what flight is going to be tomorrow

ge of front spiral descents (med cloud height).

ight slip later if front slows down.

t. Paul & Keith at back - unless either want a day on ground.

same. AVAPs, lidar wanted. ARIES not.

Kirsty in hot seat for very final part of sortie tomorrow. So Paul might have to become CVI for a short bit.

are going to do most of the pack-up, but will need assistance from all either before the flight or just after on Monday.

plane & van on Monday.

er than yesterday only 6.5 to 7.5 max - not developing further. How about profiling up/down through a cloud?

ne off for lunch

/pack up tomorrow passed on

orrow after flight, we would like some people to stay and help

what time you land on Mon, we may have 12 BAES people to show round the a/c too

6 + nt - <No topic is set >

you in the profile again?

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FAAM_MS3

FAAM_MS3

you let Doug know that the sonde message was only part complete (ie the one sent to Met DB)? Thks

cloud tops now?

ly lunch.

ghurt has not exploded.

we turn for turret

@i.love.debian.org] has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 600 seconds]

@i.love.debian.org] has joined #faam146

6 + nt - <No topic is set >

er than yesterday only 6.5 to 7.5 max - not developing further. How about profiling up/down through a cloud?
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'pack up tomorrow passed on
orrow after flight, we would like some people to stay and help
what time you land on Mon, we may have 12 BAES people to show round the a/c too

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FAAM_MS3

FAAM_MS3

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cloud tops now?

ly lunch.

ughurt has not exploded.

we turn for turret

@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Ping timeout: 600 seconds]

@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146

or ETA please?

@i.love.debian.org) has quit IRC [Quit: User pushed the X - because it's Xtra, baby]

e still not complete, only goes as far as - 61616 FAAM CONST B507

@i.love.debian.org) has joined #faam146

#faam146 by photon.cas.manchester.ac.uk

ing at 15:15

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B507

Date: 31 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
2. First signs of icing on AOA ports of Turb Probe at 12:05
- 3.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS – 17 x satpics, KB

Satcom H – not used

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Cloud Physics Flight Log B507

Date:31/01/2010	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:08:00:00	DAU1 Time:same	DAU2 Time:same	AUX1 Time:same	AUX2 Time:same
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2+SID3		2DC	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.34	Vref (>7V):	7.74	El#1 V (>1):	0.39	El#1 V (>1):	4.72	Comms2?:	y	El#1 V (>1):	-2.0
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.2	El#32 V (>1):	1.31	El#32 V (>1):	2.85	Comms2?:	Y	El#32 V (>1):	-1.9
			Sheath flow	13.99	El#64 V (>1)	1.21	El#64 V (>1)	1.67				
			Spectra ok?	Y								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
08:09:32			15									
08:10:44			20									
08:12:04			30									
08:13:15			40									
08:19:57				ZERO								
10:37:27	FL200											Start Run 1
10:38:00				25	0.2						Noise	
10:40:00				25	0.2						Noise	
10:42:00				30							Noise	
10:44:00				35							Noise	
10:46:00				Noise							Noise	
10:48:00				20							Noise	
10:50:00				20							Noise	
10:52:00				20							Noise	
10:54:00				20							Noise	
10:56:00				30							Noise	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
10:57:50	FL200			20								End of Run & Start Profile 1
10:59:00	FL190			35								
11:00:00	FL180			40								
11:02:48	FL150			75?								
11:03:42	FL140			75?								
11:04:40	FL130			100?								
11:05:42	FL120			60								
11:06:42	FL110			55								
11:07:42	FL100			40								
11:08:42	FL090			35								
11:09:39	FL080			20								
11:10:28	FL070			15								
11:11:25	FL060			25								
11:12:15	FL050			15								
11:13:07	FL040			5								
11:14:10	FL030			25								
11:15:04	FL020			20								
11:16:05	FL010			30								
11:17:53	50'			30								End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2
11:19:28	2000'											End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2
11:20:00				40							Noise	
11:22:00				30								
11:24:00				40		0.0004					0.1	
11:26:00				25								
11:28:00				30								
11:30:00				35							Noise	
11:32:00				35							Noise	
11:33:06												End of Run
11:35:15	FL037											Start Run 3
11:36:30				30								End of run
11:39:17	FL046	Error										Start Run
11:41:12												Start Run 5
11:45:00		Error		15								Serial connection problem on CDP corrected
11:50:00	FL052			5								
11:54:00		20	30	240				500	25	12	700	
11:56:00		10	25	10				200	100	12	600	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
11:58:00		30	35	5		0.08		500	800	1	600	
11:58:47												End of Run
12:01:54	FL062											Start Run 6
12:02:00				15								
12:04:00		3	47	15		0.1		500	200	1	200	
12:08:00		2	45	3		0.12		400	800	9	50	
12:10:00		25	35	75		0.04		500	800	8	600	
12:12:00		12	25	130		0.02		50	800	8	10	
12:14:00		5	35	4				10	800	8	100	
12:16:00		20	25	30				200	250	1	300	
12:18:00				15								
12:19:05												End of Run
12:22:04	FL067											Start Run 7
12:23:00		5										
12:25:00		5										
12:27:00		8	30	5							100	
12:29:00		5	35	50		0.01		300	800	9	100	
12:31:00				2								
12:33:00				3								
12:35:00				3								
12:37:00				3								
12:39:00				10								
12:41:00				2								
12:42:06												End of Run
12:45:44	FL072											Start Run 8
12:46:00		18	20	15				500	75	12	200	
12:50:00		20	35	15				500	100	12	500	
12:51:17												End of Run
12:55:21	FL077											Start Run 9
12:56:00		10	25	15				130	800	1/8	200	
12:58:00		10	40	60		0.04		50	800	8	300	
13:00:07												End of Run
13:02:36	FL082											Start Run 10
13:03:00				20								
13:05:00		1	40	65		0.03		50	800	8	50	
13:06:02												End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
13:09:26	FL082											Start Run 11
13:10:00				30								
13:12:00		2	50	2		0.005		2	800	1/8	5	
13:14:26												End of Run
13:16:11	FL082											Start Run 12
13:17:00		25	37	80		0.04		1000	800	1/8	50	
13:19:00				160		0.08		400	800	8	50	
13:21:00												End of Run
13:24:43	FL087											Start Run 13
13:25:00				20								
13:27:00				1								
13:28:30												End of Run
13:31:48	FL088											Start Run 14
13:32:00				4								
13:34:00				30		0.02		90	800	1/8	1200	
13:36:00				30								
13:37:01												End of Run
13:40:35	FL088											Start Run 15
13:41:00				30								
13:43:00		8	50	500		0.25		600	800	1/8	250	
13:44:48												End of Run
13:48:35	FL088											Start Run 16
13:49:00				3								
13:51:00		1	50	400		0.15		1000	800	1/8	150	
13:52:55												End of Run
13:56:20	FL090											Start Run 17
13:57:00				25								
13:59:00		1	50	25		0.125		25	800	8	20	
14:00:30												End of Run
14:04:15	FL082											Start Run 18
14:05:00				7								
14:07:00		1	50	30		0.1		400	800	8	15	
14:08:25												End of Run
14:12:26	FL082											Start Run 19
14:13:00				20								
14:15:00		0.1	15	2		0.07		300	800	8	5	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
14:16:10												End of Run
14:22:15	FL120			50								Start Profile 3
14:23:20	FL110			25		0.07		15	300	1	20	
14:24:27	FL100			10								
14:25:33	FL090			1								
14:26:36	FL080	0.1	30	600		0.12		150	800	8	10	
14:27:43	FL070	14	20	40		0.02		1	800	8	1	
14:32:43	FL060			210		0.02		200	800	8	2	
14:33:55	FL050			10								
14:39:24	FL040	6	35	190		0.02		15	800	8	140	
14:41:12	FL030			Noise								
14:42:11	FL020			Noise								Ch1 noise PCASP
14:43:23	FL010			Noise								
14:44:58	50'			Noise								End of profile

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:		N/A
	Flow:		
2DC	EI#1:	-2.0	
	EI#32:	-1.5	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.3	Some Ch1 Noise on occasions
	Flow:		
CDP	Laser V:	2.98	
FFSSP	Ref V:		N/A
SID 3	Laser V:		Rebooted several times
Rack Equipment			

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	Bnnn	Date	dd mmm 2010	Operator		Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
10:37:27	1	Launch	464.50 -38.10 36.21 343.90 25.00 0.80 -6.506800 58.502700 6113.10
10:45:03	1	Land	1004.37 2.43 78.62 355.23 10.49 -9.11 -6.472969 58.431960 99999.00
			End drop time override : 456.3. Surface alt unknown NOT ticked
14:21:54	2	Launch	643.50 -21.90 27.00 339.90 88.20 -11.60 -6.494400 58.650800 3668.50
14:26:35	2	Land	1003.20 2.30 81.34 333.08 13.83 -12.36 -6.467199 58.612747 254.82
			Surface alt unknown NOT ticked

Core Chemistry Log

Date: 31 Jan 2010

Flight: B507

Operator:

Doug Anderson

Page 1 of 1

In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

		<i>Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv</i>	<i>Nominally 34000 Hz</i>	<i>Nominally 7.5 Torr</i>	<i>Nominally 35 - 40 °C</i>
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)
01/30/2010 14:52:58	Previous Flight	60.875	32561.07	N/A	N/A
01/31/2010 09:38:50	Pre-Flight/Gnd	67.914	34392.46	7.52	35.42
09:42:46	Pre-Flight/Gnd	67.898	34387.46	7.51	35.53
10:18:39	FL200	65.899	33764.13	7.09	35.40
10:55:58	FL200	63.466	32980.60	7.05	35.48
11:22:35	1800 ft	63.090	33353.77	7.51	35.49
12:18:27	6300 ft	52.104	32770.93	7.52	37.39
12:29:36	6800 ft	51.178	32825.46	7.53	37.81
13:25:57	8800 ft	51.452	32436.80	7.52	38.69
14:07:44	8300 ft	50.902	32230.70	7.51	39.46
14:58:05	FL200	49.886	31924.37	7.04	39.8
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv) : 23
 NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv) : 0.47
 Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv) : 0.27

CO Calibrations on automatic repeat? : NO Interval set? : n/a

CO Time synch 08:07:03
 CO Zero valve on 08:59:50 - 09:09:50

12:18:27 CO cal seemed low so a second, similar result, was done after altitude change)

D20100131_103727.1 092819160 CONSTRAIN, B507 none, none

Range corrected signal - 120 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 120 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Range corrected signal - 96 profiles

Ch0

Ch1

Time after midnight (minutes)

0900 on Sat 30 Jan

0930 on Sat 30 Jan

1000 on Sat 30 Jan

1030 on Sat 30 Jan

1100 on Sat 30 Jan

1130 on Sat 30 Jan

1200 on Sat 30 Jan

1230 on Sat 30 Jan

1300 on Sat 30 Jan

1330 on Sat 30 Jan

1430 on Sat 30 Jan

1500 on Sat 30 Jan

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 0900 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1000 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1200 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1300 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 30 Jan 2010 1500 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 0900 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1000 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1200 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1300 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 30 Jan 2010 1500 UTC

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